

STROBE Statement—Checklist of items that should be included in reports of *cross-sectional studies*

	Item No	Recommendation	Page N°
Title and abstract	1	(a) Clearly indicate that this is a cross-sectional quantitative study in the title and/or abstract.	01
		(b) Include in the summary an accurate and balanced description of the purpose, method, key results, and conclusions regarding the relationship between energy drink consumption and sleep quality.	01
Introduction			
Background/rationale	2	Explain the social and health context of energy drink consumption among university students, justifying the analysis of the relationship between energy drink consumption and sleep quality in the context of a cross-sectional study.	02
Objectives	3	Present clear objectives: general and specific, highlighting the main hypothesis of the relationship between variables.	02
Methods			
Study design	4	Describe the non-experimental, cross-sectional, correlational design, emphasizing the sequence of phases in the quantitative approach.	04
Setting	5	Detail the geographical scope (universities in Chiclayo), target population (university students aged between 18 and 34 years old), data collection period, and inclusion/exclusion criteria.	04
Participants	6	(a) Specify inclusion/exclusion criteria and detail how participants were selected and contacted (probabilistic sampling).	04
Variables	7	Operationally define each variable: energy drink consumption (with dimensions: consumption, motives, and perceived effects) and sleep quality (with dimensions: sleep duration, sleep efficiency, and daytime consequences).	05
Data sources/ measurement	8*	Specify the sources of information (validated questionnaires by three experts) and the procedure for measuring each dimension and indicator.	05
Bias	9	Explain any measures taken to minimize selection or response biases.	N/A
Study size	10	Justify the sample size (373) and the calculation formula used.	04
Quantitative variables	11	Describe the treatment of quantitative variables: low, medium, and high levels based on scores in the questionnaires.	N/A
Statistical methods	12	(a) Indicate the statistical methods used: descriptive analysis, correlation coefficient, and software used (Excel and SPSS).	05
		(b) Explain whether subgroup analyses were performed by dimensions of the variables.	05
		(c) Clarify how missing data were handled (if none, specify).	N/A
		(d) Indicate whether the sampling design was considered in the analysis (not applicable).	N/A
		(e) Mention whether sensitivity analyses were conducted (not applicable).	N/A
Results			
Participants	13*	(a) Report the number of eligible, surveyed, and analyzed individuals (373) and detail any losses, if applicable.	N/A
		(b) Explain the reasons for non-participation (not applicable).	N/A
		(c) Consider including a flow diagram of the sample (optional).	N/A

Descriptive data	14*	(a) Describe the characteristics of the participants: age, place of residence, health status, consumption and sleep quality related with energy drinks.	04
		(b) Indicate the amount of missing data by variable (not applicable if none).	N/A
Outcome data	15*	Present results for each variable: levels of energy drinks consumption and sleeping quality.	06
Main results	16	(a) Show the correlation values between variables and dimensions, specifying statistical significance.	07, 08
		(b) Clarify categories used in continuous variables if applicable.	N/A
		(c) Not applicable to translate to absolute risk.	N/A
Other analyses	17	Report any other correlation or contrast analyses, if conducted.	N/A
Discussion			
Key results	18	Summarize the main findings, linking them to the objectives and comparing them with the reviewed literature.	09
Limitations	19	Discuss limitations: potential biases, lack of relationship found, and possible external factors explaining the results.	N/A
Interpretation	20	Interpret the findings cautiously, considering the available evidence and the study's contributions to the local issue.	09
Generalizability	21	Discuss the generalization of results to similar contexts in mining districts.	09
Other information			
Funding	22	Indicate the source of funding (if applicable) and describe the role of the institution or individuals involved in the funding and supervision of the work.	11

*Give information separately for exposed and unexposed groups.

Note: An Explanation and Elaboration article discusses each checklist item and gives methodological background and published examples of transparent reporting. The STROBE checklist is best used in conjunction with this article (freely available on the Web sites of PLoS Medicine at <http://www.plosmedicine.org/>, Annals of Internal Medicine at <http://www.annals.org/>, and Epidemiology at <http://www.epidem.com/>). Information on the STROBE Initiative is available at www.strobe-statement.org.